

Expression of Type IV Collagen in the Placenta in Undifferentiated Displasia Connecting Tissue

Expresión de Colágeno Tipo IV en la Placenta en Tejido Conectivo de Displasia Indiferenciada

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Abstract

In the preparations of women in childbirth with undifferentiated connective tissue dysplasia, positive structures to type IV collagen were revealed. A pronounced immunopositive reaction (+++) was observed by us in the subendothelial layer of the vessels of the chorionic villi, the stroma of the villi and cells. The area of expression of type IV collagen in women in the control group was $1363.9 \pm 14.9 \mu\text{m}^2$. The expression of type IV collagen significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) increased in women with connective tissue dysplasia syndrome - $3824.16 \pm 16.9 \mu\text{m}^2$.

Key words: type IV collagen, placenta, undifferentiated connective tissue dysplasia, pregnancy, immunohistochemistry, stroma, chorionic villae.

Resumen

En los preparados de parturientas con displasia indiferenciada del tejido conjuntivo se revelaron estructuras positivas al colágeno tipo IV. Observamos una reacción inmunopositiva pronunciada (+++) en la capa subendotelial de los vasos de las vellosidades coriónicas, el estroma de las vellosidades y las células. El área de expresión del colágeno tipo IV en las mujeres del grupo control fue de $1363,9 \pm 14,9 \mu\text{m}^2$. La expresión de colágeno tipo IV aumentó significativamente ($p \leq 0,05$) en mujeres con síndrome de displasia del tejido conectivo - $3824,16 \pm 16,9 \mu\text{m}^2$.

Palabras clave: colágeno tipo IV, placenta, displasia indiferenciada del tejido conectivo, embarazo, inmunohistoquímica, estroma, villas coriónicas.

Collagens are the main proteins of the extracellular matrix, and collagen fibrils form structures that resist stretching. There are 12 types of collagen known. Collagens are made up of three chains, which are very rich in glycine and proline. The role of proline is to stabilize the helical conformation of the strands, while glycine allows the coiled strands to adhere tightly to each other. Collagen contains nonessential amino acids and very small amounts of methionine, tyrosine, histidine. Collagen contains almost no tryptophan and cysteine. In addition to collagen fibers, glycosaminoglycans are present in the intercellular substance of the connective tissue: proteoglycans and glycoproteins, which are synthesized by mast cells. Mast cells synthesize heparin. Collagen synthesis is provided by connective tissue fibroblasts. The maturation of synthesized collagen includes 2 stages: intracellular and extracellular. Collagen breakdown occurs slowly, under the influence of metalloproteinase: Ca^{2+} , Zn^{2+} -dependent collagenase breaks down the bonds within the collagen molecule, then the proteins are denatured and are influenced by proteolytic enzymes. In the intercellular substance, collagen binds to fibronectin; however, fibronectin itself can bind to cells and heparin. When collagen breaks down, hydroxyproline is formed, the amount of which can increase with accelerated breakdown and disruption of biosynthesis, development of fibrosis and collagenosis.

Collagen type IV is the main component of basement membranes. The function of type IV collagen is to maintain tissue structure during embryogenesis, remodeling and regeneration. The type IV collagen molecule is a ligand for integrins, receptors on the cell surface, providing cell adhesion, migration and differentiation. Collagen provides tissue strength, cell adhesion and cell proliferation.

Biosynthesis of type IV collagen occurs in all structures of the placenta already at the early stages of development of the placental complex: cytotrophoblast, decidual cells, endometrial stromal cells, vascular wall cells [Autio-Harmanen H., 1991].

We have not found any studies aimed at studying the immunoexpression of type IV collagen in undifferentiated connective tissue dysplasia in the literature.

Purpose of the study

To identify the expression of type IV collagen in the placenta of puerperas with undifferentiated connective tissue dysplasia.

The study included 120 women with undifferentiated connective tissue dysplasia and 100 women with physiological pregnancy. An immunohistochemical study of the placenta of puerperas for type IV collagen was carried out. Placenta sections were fixed in buffered 10% formalin. Immunohistochemical reactions were carried out according to a special technique with antigens unmasking in a microwave oven on serial paraffin sections. From paraffin blocks, histological sections with a thickness of 5 μm were prepared, which were fixed in glass, previously coated with an adhesive (APES-acetone). Endogenous peroxidase was blocked with 3% hydrogen peroxide solution in dewaxed sections. Antigen unmasking was carried out in an oven for 20 minutes at 600 V in a dissolved citrate buffer with pH 6.0. Rabbit polyclonal antibodies specific to type IV collagen (Imtek, Russia) were used as primary specific antibodies. A universal kit containing a conjugate of horseradish peroxidase with sheep antibodies specific to rabbit IgG, IgA, IgM (Imtek, Russia) was used as secondary antibodies. The results of the immunohistochemical picture were assessed qualitatively (Fig. 1, 2). Systemic morphometric analysis of histological preparations was performed using the hardware-software complex "Video-Test Morphology 5.0".

When staging an immunohistochemical reaction on sections of the placenta of puerperas, we found structures that were immunopositive to type IV collagen. In the placenta of women in childbirth with the physiological course of pregnancy, a moderate histochemical reaction was noted in the subendothelial layer of the vascular walls of the chorionic villi. Chorionic villus stroma and fibroblasts are immunopositive to type IV collagen.

In the placenta preparations of women in childbirth with undifferentiated connective tissue dysplasia, positive structures to type IV collagen were also revealed. A pronounced immunopositive reaction (+++) was observed by us in the subendothelial layer of the vessels of the chorionic villi, the stroma of the villi and cells.

We have calculated the area of expression of immunoreactive structures. The area of expression of type IV collagen in women in the control group was $1363.9 \pm 14.9 \mu\text{m}^2$. The expression of type IV collagen significantly (p

≤ 0.05) increased in women with connective tissue dysplasia syndrome - $3824.16 \pm 16.9 \mu\text{m}^2$.

Fig. 1. Type IV collagen in the placenta during the physiological course of pregnancy (immunohistochemical method, magnification $\times 400$).

Fig. 2. Expressed expression of type IV collagen in the placenta in connective tissue dysplasia (immunohistochemical method, magnification $\times 400$).

Discussion

The study of the peculiarities of the course of pregnancy and the state of the placenta in the experimental model of the Ehlers-Danlos syndrome showed a decrease in the mass of the placenta, a change in the vascular structure, the phenomenon of ischemia and necrosis. Using the method of electron microscopy, it was found that the basement membranes of the capillaries of the villi have an abnormal structure [Yoshizawa T, 2018].

Through platelets, collagen indirectly affects cells, vascular permeability, blood coagulation factors and immunity. Collagen enhances platelet aggregation and induces platelet aggregation in vascular damage. It was found that platelets have three receptors for collagen: the indirect GP1b glycoprotein for initial engagement, the GP VI glycoprotein for activation, and $\alpha 2\text{b}1$ glycoprotein for full adhesion. In the process of platelet aggregation under the influence of collagen, ATP, ADP, serotonin and other mediators are released, which enhance the proliferation of fibroblasts and smooth muscles. Collagen binds to the C1 and C3 components of the complement, promoting leukocyte chemotaxis.

In clinical studies, weak expression of type I collagen in the wall of endometrioid ovarian cysts, moderate expression of type III collagen in the diffuse aspect of the stroma and cytoplasm of fibroblasts of the cyst capsule, pronounced expression of type IV collagen in the sub-endothelial layer of the vascular wall in women with undifferentiated connective tissue dysplasia³.

In our immunohistochemical study of the placentas of women with connective tissue dysplasia, an increase in the expression of type IV collagen in the chorionic villi stroma was revealed, which is evidence of abundant vascularization and ongoing neoangiogenesis.

Conclusions

Thus, type IV collagen is found in the placenta of postpartum women both with the physiological course of pregnancy and in women with undifferentiated connective tissue dysplasia. In patients with undifferentiated connective tissue dysplasia, abundant vascularization of the chorionic villi and the ongoing process of neoangiogenesis are observed.

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